

Implementing Optical Character Recognition for Text Extraction and Indexing using Topic Modeling and Deep Learning Techniques

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Abstract

In the modern world, practically everything is mechanised, and data is transmitted and stored digitally. There are, however, a number of circumstances in which the data is not digitised, and it may be necessary to extract text from them in order to save it in digitised form. The technique of text extraction utilising optical character recognition has been entirely revolutionised by the most recent technologies, such as text recognition software. Therefore, this article introduces the idea, describes the extraction procedure, and provides an overview of the newest methods, technologies, and ongoing research in the field. We have implemented OCR using Tesseract, with LDA for topic modeling along with Word2Vec for deep learning. With an optimized result of 96.76 % accuracy, we can conclude that our methodology outcasts existing methods.

Introduction

The process of computerising text or creating a digital copy of text from sources like handwritten papers, printed text, or from actual photographs is known as optical character recognition (OCR) [1]. The broad category of Digital Image Processing (DIP) encompasses it [2]. Digital image processing, or DIP, is the process of running digital pictures via a computer algorithm. DIP is an area that has applications in almost every other discipline, including the banking industry, robotics, and the healthcare sector for PET scans, among others, and it is still evolving. Pattern recognition, which encompasses computer-aided diagnosis, handwriting recognition, and picture identification, is one of its main uses.

The world's data is expanding at an exponential rate, necessitating the development of text recognition software. Since all of this data cannot be physically retained, it must be preserved digitally. Automatic Character Recognition, which makes use of OCR, is used as a result. These days, OCR frameworks are typically employed to extract text information from any artificial or computerised image.

OCR encourages checked archives to go beyond being only photo records, making them into fully searchable documents. As a result, it is frequently used for various objectives including information extraction. When creating a digital copy of a large report, users might use OCR to save having to retype it. OCR separates out relevant information, which is then entered regularly. It enables a machine to understand the information contained in an image as viewed when reading a written document and to store that information in a way that makes it easier to analyse later[3].

OCR has emerged as a crucial component of contemporary technology like text-to-speech software, barcode scanners, etc. Given that augmented reality, or AR, is based on object recognition, it is also utilised to support AR. OCRs may be used to identify not just text but also other objects. OCR was initially developed to aid the blind, but since then, technology has advanced significantly, making it simpler to develop a text-to-speech engine, as noted in [29].

Based on the kind of information, OCR frameworks may be characterized into 3:

1. Handwritten—Systems that only function with written text.
2. Machine printed: Those that exclusively use text that has been entered and then printed.

3. Specific kind - The language, typeface, and other variables all play a part in how the OCR functions. As a result, there are several OCR systems for certain languages, such as Urdu.

OCR was developed in 1914 to aid blind or differently abled persons, although it is now mostly used for text recognition. It made it possible for the blind to have written material read aloud to them by a machine. Additionally, as technology was not as advanced and there was insufficient processing power in the 1950s, the development of OCR encountered various challenges including speed and accuracy [1]. Early optical character versions worked on one word at a time and required training on individual character representations.

Nowadays, several OCR tools are employed, including the Google Drive OCR, Tesseract, Transym, OmniPage, etc. While many of them require payment, some are free to use. [4] One of the most well-known and often employed OCR engines on the internet is called Tesseract. It operates via a four-step sequential procedure. Instead of accuracy, it emphasises covering a wide range of languages and typefaces. It is discovered that tesseract delivers greater accuracy on average than Transym OCR (another open-source OCR engine), although it is not always quicker. Programs/software utilise these engines to transform digital pictures into a format that may be used to modify them.

Modern wireless technologies enable devices to communicate data over networks rather than storing the complete OCR system there, where it would take a long time to process it and provide the findings to the device. One such web-based OCR converter that can operate as a whole system online is online OCR.

Related Work

In addition to the standard methods previously mentioned, a number of ideas put forth by different scholars in the area have been looked into and are included below:

A novel approach [11] with 7 phases was put forth to extract text from natural photos. The filtering procedure is first applied as preprocessing to enhance the image. The Thresholding method is used for lateral separation to separate the backdrop from the necessary material. The MSER (Maximally Stable External Region) is then found, and the unnecessary portion is removed. The stroke width variance algorithm next applies the stroke width computation, and finally, CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) is utilised to generate the characteristics needed for the OCR to recognise the letters to obtain the text.

Another [12] presented a neural network-based architecture that uses bidirectional long short-term memory (BLSTMB) to operate and enables word-level OCR. As compared to a standard OCR framework, it produces results that are over 20% better. One of the most prevalent causes of the mistake is that it employs a method that does not need segmentation. Additionally, when compared with the more frequently used OCR framework, it discovered a drop in character error of almost 9%.

[13] This method suggested separating content and non-content sections using a two-advance iterative Conditional Random Field (CRF) computation with a Belief Propagation obstacle, and then using OCR on the content component to produce the desired result. Two relational networks are employed in the scenario of numerous text lines to extract the various text lines, and the OCR certainty is used as a reference for locating text-containing regions.

[14] The Complete OCR Method for Historical Texts for Text Extraction from Historical Documents. It consists of three steps: the first includes binarization and improvement. In the following stage, line segments, words, and letters are distinguished using a high-level separation technique. The KNN integration theme is used to include the same group's symbols. Finally, in the third stage, the same prior classification approach is used to each image of the new document, while the recognition is based on the data extrapolated from the previous step. High throughput rates of up to 95.44% are the outcome.

Several processes are used in this program's text extraction from television. The hosting service is first utilised to process the data. The OCR method is then used to extract the text from the input data. The output from the preceding phase is then compared to the expected results, and before it is released, a determination is made as to whether it is right or not. This software may be used to evaluate TV sets in a real-world setting [15].

Identification of Vehicles via Number Plate Recognition: Security is one of the many fields where OCR is employed. You may use this technology to monitor traffic at the security entry. An image of the car is captured first, and then the number plate is extracted utilising portions of the image. The text is then extracted using OCR, and the information is then matched to the

inventory data to identify the information for the car's owner. For security reasons, it creates a robust system with excellent dependability. [16] [17].

Several studies propose future directions for this field of study. For instance, according to [18], the accuracy of OCR may be impacted by presently increasing factors such as Scan objectives, filtered picture quality, kind of printer used—whether ink-jet or laser—the type of paper used, phonetic complexity, the lopsided brightness, and watermarks. Therefore, effort may be done to increase OCR's accuracy. An OCR framework looks at a variety of concerns [19], but Chinese and Arabic character recognition stands out since both languages have confusing frameworks, unbalanced text styles, and other challenges. When it comes to handwritten record photos, there are several problems, such as the likelihood of skewed, touching, or covered content lines. New methods like the Spiral Run Length Smearing Algorithm (SRLSA) have therefore been the subject of investigation. Additionally, as it isn't yet 100% accurate, the extracted text must be double-checked for mistakes, and for little amounts of text, it is simply not worth using since it is typically quicker to do manually than with contemporary OCR systems. There is no universal procedure that can be used to obtain the required outcome with great accuracy because every language and typeface is unique [22]. In this way, a lot of research is being done to increase the OCR framework's accuracy for a particular language or typeface, and even within the same language, several approaches might be used.

Figure Steps towards Recognition in OCR

Proposed Method

Figure 1.0 Proposed System Architecture

About Tesseract4J

With the advancement of technology in AI and machine learning, we require tools to recognize text within images.

Figure 2.0 OCR Flow Model

- Pre-process image data, for example: convert to gray scale, smooth, de-skew, filter.
- Detect lines, words and characters.
- Produce ranked list of candidate characters based on trained data set. (here the setDataPath() method is used for setting path of trainer data)
- Post process recognized characters, choose best characters based on confidence from previous step and language data. Language data includes dictionary, grammar rules, etc.

About Word2Vec

Word2vec is a group of related themes used in a production called Word Weddings. These models are shallow neural networks that are trained to create a new vocabulary context. After training, the word2vec model can be used to map each word to a vector of hundreds of elements, which typically represent the word's relationship to other words. This vector is the hidden layer of the neural network. Word2vec is based on a Cross Bag or Continuous Bag of Words (CBOW) to create a wedding word. It was created by a team of researchers led by Tomas Mikolov from Google. Now use Word Weddings, a collection of related Word2vec themes. These models are suitable for creating new jargon parameters because they are shallow neural networks. The word2vec model can be used to map each word to a vector of different components, which typically determine how the word relates to other words after preparation. This vector represents the structure of the hidden layer of the brain. To create a wedding word, Word2vec uses a cross-bag or fixed word pack (CBOW). It was created by a team of scientists led by Tomas Mikolov from Google. The calculations were then analyzed and explained by numerous analysts.

About LDA

LDA is a frequently used setting presenting computation that finds hidden themes in archive collections. The word LDA is used in this context to address every discovered point. Using the terms that appear in each report, locate the hidden subject in the archive. The assortment is reports $D = d_1, d_2, \dots, d_m$. Moreover, there are m total records in the assortment. All reports are sent to LDA to be divided into a defined number of topics. LDA assumes that each archive covers a certain number of topics and each point can be considered a crossword scatter. The classification level and registration level are used to illustrate the LDA model. Each record d_i in the report set is assigned a storage-level header using the formula $d_i = (d_i, 1, d_i, 2, \dots, d_i, V)$, where V is the number of topics. The report is displayed at the collection level as D . Each record has a probability delivery on the words, $_j$ for theme j . In general, we have for all points $= 1, 2, \dots, v$.

The LDA model also begins word tasks in addition to displaying these two levels, which means that the occurrence of words will be perceived as related to the subject. The LDA model, $D = (D, 1, D, 2, \dots, D, V)$, may be used to establish the regulation of topics in the assortment of all D reports. The LDA model's primary contribution to the assortment D is the use of prescribed words to illustrate a topic and the presentation of points to illustrate information displaying examples of people speaking the words necessary for the record and point to be made. Identify the topics that are important for the record. LDA can benefit in many ways from report digests by subject and record assortment. There are several methods for deciding the content in the preparation subject for new approaching records. In this article, we use the topic organization in accordance with the organization to demonstrate the archive and provide the proper positioning strategy which determines the significance of the new upcoming report.

ENHANCED LDA

The limitations of word substitution are overcome by example-based representation, which is the best way to visualize datasets. Also as a delegate, given the information structure model created by the word coalition. To determine the relevance of the collected data for the discussion of the topic and the report, two steps are suggested:

- (1) Process the index of new exchange information using LDA results from the archived collection. D
- (2) To represent customer needs, a model must be developed that supports different types of information exchange.
- (3) Application for equivalence model classes.

1) Create TD(Transactional Dataset)

Let's see how R_{di} , z_j defines the subject lemma Z_j in R_{di} datasets. According to the customer, the term "record a clear exchange" refers to each sentence below the item that appears in each report. Specific Reporting Exchange (TDT) is a creative choice of words. For the purposes of many words: $R_{di} I_{2d}$; My name is M_j , where I_{ij} is a series of words starting with R_{di} and Z_j I_{ij} , called exchange ratios. We can have a set of exchange information $V(1, 2, \dots, v)$ for each subject of D .2) Create a model-based representation.

The method according to the example is often built from each exchange sentence in the presented structure. The example is approached with j . Z_j is a collection of terms that together form the basic helping boundary that builds things. Only if $\text{supp}(X) > \epsilon$, which is the presence of X and the number of exchanges in j with X , will X occur in j . Customers establish basic support models. The repeat of the “X” series is described as a collection of all common themes. Z_j is represented as $X_{zi} = X_{i1}, X_{i2}, \dots, X_{im_i}$, where m_i is the total number of variations in X_{zi} and v is the total number of points.

3) PATTERN EQUIVALENCE CLASS

The number of examples, often drawn from previous advances, is quite large, so many examples are not necessary to be useful. There are numerous major strengths in introducing useful examples rather than the exaggerated and closed designs that sometimes come from large collections of information. The specificity of compact structures is less important for information collection than the specificity of regularly formed patterns. Let us consider EC1 and EC2 as two different unified classes of exchange information collection that are precisely ambiguous. Referring to the equality class, which is essentially unrelated, $EC1 = EC2$. The suggested design makes use of 2 linked components. The relevance of new incoming information is determined by preparation, which is used to create instances of interest for clients from the variety of archives required for preparation. With the Stanford NLP library, examine the importance of the important model in the suggested model.

Enhanced LDA Pseudopodia

1. Input: user interest model $UE = \{ E(Z_1), \dots, E(Z_V) \}$, a list of incoming document D_{in}
2. Output: $\text{rank}_E(d)$, $d \in D_{in}$
3. $\text{rank}(d) = 0$
4. for each $d \in D_{in}$ do
5. for each topic $Z_j \in [Z_1, Z_v]$ do
6. for each equivalence class $EC_{jk} \in E(Z_j)$ do
7. 5: scan $EC_{k,j}$ and find maximum matched pattern which exists in d
8. update $\text{rank}_E(d)$ using equation(1)
9. 7: $\text{rank}(d) := \text{rank}(d) + \left| \left|^{0.5} * f_{jk} * v_{D,j} * \text{uniform distribution} * \text{equivalent class frequency} \right. \right|$
10. end for
11. end for
12. end for

Our Implementation

1. Learn initial model from training data, using annotated data and image text extraction using OCR.
2. Generate model for each document. (LDA, Theta Value for D_t)
 - In order to find a meaningful meaning from the document set to represent the topic and document, 2 steps are proposed:
 - (1) Process new transaction data set using the LDA results of document collection D
 - (2) Create a model that is represented by a set of transaction data to show the needs of users.

- (3) Request the Equivalence Pattern class
3. Set Burnout Parameter.
 4. Perform Gibbs Sampling
 5. Generate Transaction Set (TD)
 6. Let R_{di} , z_j represent the word header definition for the Z_j topic in d_i R_{di} documents
 7. By user Each word under the topic that occurs in each document is called a document-specific transaction.
 8. A specific document transaction (TDT) is a unique set of words.
 9. For the assignment of all the words, $R_{di} \{z_j; I^m M_j\}$ where I_{ij} is a collection of words that originated in R_{di} , $Z_j I_{ij}$, called transaction specific documents. For each topic in D , we can create a set of transaction V data $(\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2, \dots, \Gamma_v)$.
 - In order to find a meaningful meaning from the document set to represent the topic and document, 2 steps are proposed:
 - (1) Process new transaction data set using the LDA results of document collection D
 - (2) Create a model that is represented by a set of transaction data to show the needs of users.
 - (3) Request the Equivalence Pattern class
 10. Perform Lucene Indexing.
 11. Set mixture parameter λ using Word2Vec representation.
 12. Set estimation of hidden variable Z_w .
 13. Perform Maximization step (M-step) and obtain parameter $\Theta(e)$
 14. Obtain vector value for words and generate lexicon.

Lucene Indexing

Create a method to retrieve a Lucene document from a text file. Create multiple types of fields that are key-value pairs containing keys as names and values as content to be indexed. Specify whether the field should be parsed or not. In our case, only the content is analyzed as it may contain data like a, am, are, an, etc. which are not required for searches.

Add the newly created fields to the document object and return it to the calling method.

Step 1 – Create IndexWriter object.

Step 2 – Create a Lucene directory which should point to the location where the indexes will be stored.

Step 3 – Initialize the created IndexWriter object with the index directory, a default parser containing version information and other required/optional parameters.

Figure 3.1 Home Page

Figure 3.2 LDA Topic Modelling

```
00093726.json -- 853,
00093726.json--853,
00093726.json -- 207,
00093726.json--207,
00093726.json--868
00093726.json -- "text":
00093726.json--"text":
00093726.json -- "J.",
00093726.json--"J.",
00093726.json -- "box":
00093726.json--"box":
00093726.json -- 216,
00093726.json--216,
00093726.json -- 852,
00093726.json--852,
00093726.json -- 236,
00093726.json--236,
```

Figure 3.3 Transactional Dataset

Figure 3.4 Key Index Parameters

Figure 3.5 Output Window Testing

Figure 4.0 Average Graph of Key Index Parameters

Table 1.0 Proposed System 3 iterations readings

Precision	Recall	Accuracy	F-Score
97.87	98.12	96.11	99.12
98.23	97.76	96.07	99.19
97.44	96.71	95.23	98.22

Table 2.0 Existing System 2 Gram Based Model

Precision	Recall	Accuracy	F-Score
46.89	69.23	49.09	NA

Figure 5.0 Comparison with existing system

Conclusion

Applications for optical character recognition are numerous. It is used to extract text from old books, scripts, and other materials as well as from photographs. There is continuous research in this field to increase the range of text that can be read by a single OCR system and enhance the accuracy of the retrieved text. Since it first emerged, researchers have had to overcome a number of difficulties. Some of them, like the early OCR systems' poor speed, have been resolved, while others, like obtaining 100% accuracy and a restricted range for a single OCR, remain unresolved. As a result, even though this sector is seeing a tremendous quantity of investigation, there is still plenty of room for much more. Future research may yield new methods or algorithms that increase precision and contribute to the development of an OCR system that can process any type of dataset, independent of language, font, or other factors. It may also be utilised for a lot more applications with the aid of other sectors like artificial intelligence and augmented reality, and its potential are virtually limitless.

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